

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

A novel library of tagged transcription factors in *Drosophila*

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

The project will create non-human (*Drosophila melanogaster*) data exclusively. Generated data types are:

- **Sequence data:** sequences of empty vectors in genbank format and sequences of inserts (homology arms and guide RNAs) in FASTA format. Total size < 100 MB.
- **Genotype information:** (Genomic location of CRISPR modifications, inserted construct, associated gene, identity and relative location of the inserted tag, genotype of the injected fly line) in FlyBase stock ontology (OWL 2 Web Ontology Language) format. Total size < 1GB.
- **Confocal images with associated metadata:** (sample data such as tissue, developmental stage, antibodies used, etc.
- **Technical metadata:** such as microscope hardware, objective used, laser intensity, etc.) and data analysis.

Confocal stacks will be captured in CZI and stored as both CZI and OME-TIFF. On average, we will produce 20 confocal stacks per TF and we will analyse the expression 200 TFs. Estimated total size ~ 500 GB.

II. Standards and metadata

- **Confocal microscopy technical metadata:** (Microscope hardware, Image acquisition settings) will be stored as OME-XML (docs.openmicroscopy.org/ome-model/5.6.3/ome-xml/).
- **Biological metadata:** (organism, strain, developmental stage, sex, tissue and genotype) will be stored in Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) (format ebi.ac.uk/efo/).
- **Analyses:** (description of tissue expression patterns) will be stored in Flybase Fly Anatomy (FBbt) format (github.com/FlyBase/drosophila-anatomy-developmental-ontology).

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

The study will generate original primary data. Gene models and genomic coordinates will be according to FlyBase (flybase.org) genome version R6.58.

IV. Secondary use

Our resource will allow Drosophila researchers from diverse scientific backgrounds to study TFs of their choosing, in any context. This resource will serve as a blueprint for similar efforts for different gene families or in different model organisms.

V. Methods for data sharing

All data will be available through a web interface on the dedicated server. In addition, data will be available through existing, dedicated databases:

- **Sequence data:** genbank.
- **Genotype information:** FlyBase (see letter of support)
- **Confocal microscopy:** The BioImage Archive (ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/).
- **Data analyses:** (identified tissue distributions) will be submitted to FlyBase.

The resource will be published in a preprint journal early in the project. We will publicise the database in this publication, at meetings and through our network of collaborators. Digital Object Identifiers pointing to the data will be published on our server and in any publications.

VI. Proprietary data

No human, sensitive, proprietary or patentable data will be produced or used in this study. We do not foresee any restrictions or delays in data sharing.

VII. Timeframes

All data will be made available upon generation.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

- **Sequence data:** sequences of empty vectors in genbank format and sequences of inserts in FASTA format (text files).
- **Genotype data:** Genome and insert information in FlyBase stock ontology (OWL 2 Web Ontology Language) format.
- **Confocal microscopy:** Confocal stacks will be captured in CZI, a proprietary Zeiss format and stored as both CZI and OME-TIFF.